

A Study on Employees Job Satisfaction at Borax India Ltd Company

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ABSTRACT

Job satisfaction is to find the level of job satisfaction. It ultimately decides the extent of employ motivation through the development of organizational climate or environment satisfaction is specific subset of attitudes held by organizational members. It is the attitude one has towards his or her job. Stated another way, it is one's effective response to the job. Job satisfaction in a narrow sense means attitudes related to the job. It is concerned with such specific factors has salaries , supervisory action, steadiness of employment, conditions of work, and relationship between employees and employers prompt settlement of grievances, fair treatment of employer and other similar items. Job satisfaction is related to different Socio-economic and personal factors, such as: age, gender, safety and comfort, working Environment, education, duration of work etc. The present paper will highlight different factors affecting job satisfaction in borax Indian ltd company.

KEYWORDS: *Performance, safety and comfort, working Environment, education, duration of work etc*

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INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is a general attitude which is the result of many specific attitude in three areas, namely (i) specific job factors; (ii) individual characteristics; and (iii) group relationship outside the job. These factors can never be isolated from each other for analysis. The approach which since to be opted is that job satisfaction is the favourableness or unfavourableness with which employees view their works. It results when job requirements suit to the wants and expectation of the employees. (Dr. P. K. Mishra 2013).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Job satisfaction is a multifaceted construct with a variety of definitions and related concepts, which has been studied in a variety of disciplines for many years to now. Many theories and articles of interest to managers, social psychologist, and scholars, focus on job satisfaction because most people spend their life-time for work, and understanding of the factors that increase satisfaction is important to improve the well-being of individuals in this facet of the living (Gruneberg, 1997). Below is some information related to job satisfaction.

A Hawthorne study was the one of biggest study of job satisfaction . This study (1924 -1933) was conducted by the Elton Mayo of the Harvard Business School to find out the effect of various conditions of worker's productivity. These studies ultimately showed that novel changes Win work conditions temporarily increase productivity. It is called the Hawthorne Effects. This finding provided strong evidence

that people work for purposes other than pay, which paved the way for researchers to investigate other factors in job satisfaction.

Scientific management also had a significant impact on the study of job satisfaction. Principles of Scientific Management book (Taylor, 1911) was argued that there was a single best way to perform any given work task. This book contributed to a change in industrial production philosophies, causing a shift from skilled labor and piecework towards the more modern approach of assembly lines and hourly wages. Therefore industries greatly increased productivity because workers were forced to work at a faster pace. However, workers became exhausted and dissatisfied, thus leaving researchers with new questions to answer regarding job satisfaction. It should also be noted that the work of W.L. Bryan, Walter Dill Scott, and Hugo Munsterberg set the tone for Taylor's work. Some argue that Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, a motivation theory, laid the foundation for job satisfaction theory. This theory explains that people seek to satisfy five specific needs in life physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, self-esteem needs, and self-actualization. This model served as a good basis from which early researchers could develop job satisfaction theories. In a literature review, Lu, While, and Barriball (2005) mentioned the traditional model of job satisfaction focuses on all the feelings about job of an individual. However, what makes a job satisfying or dissatisfying does not depend only on the nature of the job, but also on the expectations that

individuals have of what their job should provide. Maslow (1954 cited in Huber, 2006) arranged human needs along a five level hierarchy from physiological needs, safety and security, belonging, esteem to self-actualization. In Maslow's pyramid, needs at the lower levels must be fulfilled before those rise to a higher level.

Herzberg and colleagues built Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory of job satisfaction. Theory proposed that there are two different categories of needs, which are intrinsic (motivators) and extrinsic (hygiene) factors. Theory postulates that job satisfaction and/or is dissatisfaction is the function of two need systems. Intrinsic factors are related to the job itself. Intrinsic factors seem to influence positively on job satisfaction. The motivators include advancement, growth and development, responsibility for work, challenging, recognition, and advancement.

In other words, extrinsic factors are closely related to the environment and condition of the work. The hygiene relate to job dissatisfaction including Supervision, company policy and administration, working condition and interpersonal relation. This theory has dominated in the study of job satisfaction, and become a basic for development of job satisfaction assessment.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To find the level of job satisfaction in BORAX INDIA LIMITED company.
- To find the association between job satisfaction and the performance of employee.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

Ha: There is association between job satisfaction and performance of employee.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETION

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Organizations often neglect the impact of job satisfaction towards the gravity of employees' performance. This study explains how do the multiple dimensions of job satisfaction are evaluated and further correlated with the job performance of the employees among various groups in the Automobile industry. It was observed that there is a strong correlation between the levels of job satisfaction and of Performance of an employee, in both Supervisor and Worker groups of the Automobile Industry. A sample of 100 employees was taken which contributes to about 70 of the total employees. Job satisfaction was observed higher in the supervisors' level rather than that of the Employees in workers level.(M.Shaju)-(D.Sudhashini.

CHART-1: LEVEL OF EMPLOYEES JOB SATISFACTION
34.58

From the above score chart it is found that the level of employees job satisfaction 34.58 out of total score of 50 which lies in Moderate level. Therefore, the level employees job satisfaction at BORAX INDIA LTD COMPANY in METTUPALAYAM at PONDICHERY is found to be at moderate level.

TABLE- 1 THE CHI-SQUARE TABLE FOR THE EMPLOYEES JOB SATISFACTION

Job Satisfaction Performance	Low	Modertae	High	Total
Low	0	8	4	12
Modertae	0	21	7	28
High	0	0	0	0

CHI SQUARE: 0.293

P VALUE: 0.990

From the above table it was found that chi-square value is 0.293 and p value is 0.990 > 0.05.

CONCLUSION:

A study conducted at Borax India limited company to identify the employee's opinion and job satisfaction and also helps to give suggestion for improving the level of satisfaction The cooperation from the side of the workers and management and employees are appeasable. The workers of Borax India Limited Company show a positive response on Job satisfaction .Since the main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of job satisfaction of the respondents on their performance level, it is detected that the former's impact over the latter are more in supervisor group who are holding higher ranks. satisfaction is uncovered in employees with more job experience rather than those with less expectations.

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